

Assessment of aeroacoustic simulations for the installation noise of a propeller-wing configuration in forward flight using multi-fidelity solvers

Luis Fernando Lopes De Moraes Filho^{*}, Burak Buda Turhan[†], Leone Trascinelli[‡], Djamel Rezgui[§], Mahdi Azarpeyvand[¶]
School of Civil, Aerospace and Design Engineering, University of Bristol, Bristol, BS8 1TR, UK

Andrea Franco^{||}, Roland Ewert^{**}
Institute of Aerodynamics and Flow Technology, German Aerospace Center (DLR), Lilienthalplatz 7, 38108 Braunschweig, Germany

Bin Zang^{††}
Aerospace Engineering, Queen Mary University of London, London, United Kingdom

Beckett Y. Zhou^{‡‡}
Daniel Guggenheim School of Aerospace Engineering, Georgia Institute of Technology, North Avenue, Atlanta, GA, United States

This study presents a numerical investigation into the aerodynamic and aeroacoustic characteristics of a 5-bladed propeller installed upstream of a symmetric wing in forward flight. The research aims to assess near-field flow interactions and predict far-field noise levels, using two different approaches: a Lattice-Boltzmann-Method based solver implemented in the software PowerFLOW[®], in conjunction with the Ffowcs-Williams and Hawkings acoustic analogy, and a recently developed mid-fidelity fast and non-empirical approach, realized as a hybrid Reynolds Averaged Navier Stokes - Computational Aeroacoustics method, based on rotating line-distributed propeller sources. The computational setup emulates a typical operational condition, enabling detailed examination of how the upstream propeller's wake impacts the aeroacoustic profile of the wing-propeller configuration. This work provides insights into tonal and broadband noise contributions and highlights tonal noise amplification at blade passing frequencies due to the propeller-wing interaction. Further analysis will focus on the flow field characteristics, which are anticipated to reveal interactions between wake turbulence and wing surface, leading to complex noise patterns that could be mitigated in future design optimizations. Upon completion, this study will extend the understanding of installation effects on noise generation in propeller-wing configurations, with the ultimate aim of guiding more efficient aeroacoustic designs for advanced applications.

Nomenclature

ρ	Density [kg/m ³]	f	Frequency [Hz]
θ	Polar Angle [°]	J	Advance Ratio
c	Airfoil chord	n	Propeller Rotational Rate [rev/sec]
C_Q	Torque coefficient	p	Pressure [Pa]
C_T	Thrust coefficient	p'	Pressure Fluctuation [Pa]
D	Propeller Diameter [m]	Q	Torque [Nm]

^{*}PhD Candidate, Department of Aerospace Engineering, AIAA Member

[†]Research Associate, Department of Aerospace Engineering, AIAA Member

[‡]PhD Candidate, Department of Aerospace Engineering, AIAA Member

[§]Associate Professor, Department of Aerospace Engineering, AIAA Member

[¶]Professor of Aerodynamics and Aeroacoustics in Aerospace Engineering, School of Civil, Aerospace and Design Engineering

^{||}Research Scientist

^{**}Senior Research Scientist, DLR Team Lead, AIAA Senior Member

^{††}Senior Lecturer, AIAA Member

^{‡‡}Assistant Professor, AIAA Senior Member

T	Thrust [N]	OASPL	Overall Sound Pressure Level
U_∞	Free-stream velocity	PSD	Power Spectral Density
BPF	Blade Pass Frequency	RANS	Reynolds Averaged Navier Stokes
CAA	Computational Aeroacoustics	RMS	Root Mean Square
DEP	Distributed Electric Propulsion	SPL	Sound Pressure Level
FW-H	Ffowcs-Williams & Hawkings	VR	Variable Resolution
HEP	Hybrid Electric Propulsion		

I. Introduction

THE aerospace industry is undergoing a paradigm shift toward more sustainable aviation technologies, driven by the growing need to reduce carbon emissions and increase fuel efficiency. Among the most promising advancements are Hybrid Electric Propulsion (HEP) and Distributed Electric Propulsion (DEP) systems, which are considered pivotal in reshaping the future of aviation [1, 2]. HEP systems combine conventional combustion engines with electric motors, offering an intermediary step toward the complete electrification of aircraft. By optimizing the use of both power sources, HEP systems aim to improve efficiency, reduce emissions, and provide greater operational flexibility [3, 4]. In contrast, DEP systems rely on the use of multiple smaller, distributed electric motors, each driving its own propeller. This configuration offers several aerodynamic advantages, including enhanced lift-to-drag ratios, increased stability, and reduced stall speeds [5, 6]. These benefits make DEP systems an attractive option for future aircraft designs, especially in the context of reducing the environmental impact of aviation.

A critical aspect of DEP system design is understanding the aerodynamic interactions between the propellers and the airframe, which are more complex than those encountered in traditional propulsion systems. Distributing multiple propulsion units across the airframe markedly alters airflow patterns, thereby changing the wing's lift and drag characteristics [7, 8]. Moreover, the wake produced by each propeller interacts with its neighbors, generating vortices and flow disturbances that influence both the aerodynamic performance and the aeroacoustic signature of the system [9, 10]. These interactions are not only crucial for the performance of the propulsion system but also for understanding and mitigating the noise generated by the aircraft, which is a growing concern for the public acceptance of electric aircraft [11–13]. In fact, the aeroacoustic behaviour of DEP systems is intricately linked to the positioning and design of the propellers [14, 15]. Tonal noise, particularly at the blade-passing frequency (BPF) and its harmonics, and broadband noise from turbulent flow and vortex interactions are critical noise components in the design of quiet, efficient propulsion systems [16, 17], which could intensify by the close proximity of propellers to one another and to the airframe as well. By conducting studies on single propellers mounted on wings, researchers can isolate and understand key factors that contribute to these acoustic and aerodynamic effects, which can then be scaled to more complex multi-propeller systems [18, 19].

Given the complexity of multi-rotor interactions in DEP configurations, it is essential to consider the role of single-propeller installations as a foundational study to understand the broader challenges faced by DEP systems. Research on single propeller configurations, particularly those installed on wings, provides invaluable insights into the fundamental aerodynamic and acoustic properties that will influence the performance of more complex multi-propeller systems [20]. For example, studies on single propellers have shown that factors such as blade geometry, rotational speed, and propeller placement significantly affect both the aerodynamic loads and noise generated by the system [15]. Investigating these single propeller setups allows for a deeper understanding of how each component interacts with the surrounding flow field, a crucial step in optimizing the design of DEP systems and understanding the complexities introduced by multi-propeller systems. [21, 22]. Furthermore, the interaction between the propeller and the wing or airframe, known as the aerodynamic installation effect, plays a significant role in determining the acoustic and aerodynamic properties of the system. This effect arises when the propeller wake interacts with the wing, leading to additional noise and influencing the flow characteristics around the aircraft. [23].

In this paper, an investigation on different numerical modelling strategies for DEP is presented, which provides an initial insight on the possible sources of noise for such configurations and their modelling requirements, to aid future designers in improving current aircraft design workflows. The numerical modelling approaches considered are:

- 1) **High-fidelity Lattice Boltzmann Method (LBM).** A compressible LBM solver is used to predict both aerodynamic flow field and far-field noise. Far-field noise is computed with the solid-surface Ffowcs-Williams and Hawkings (FW-H) acoustic analogy from data on relevant solid surfaces, propagated to prescribed microphone locations, providing both tonal and broadband noise predictions.
- 2) **Mid-fidelity Reynolds Averaged Navier Stokes (RANS) – Computational Aeroacoustics (CAA) approach.** A hybrid RANS-CAA approach is considered for the prediction of perturbations over a steady background

flow field provided by a precursor steady RANS simulation. The tonal component of the aeroacoustics of installed propellers is predicted using a RANS solver that includes an Actuator Disc (AD) model, from which the aerodynamic loads on the disc are extracted for the definition of regularised line-source distributions for the CAA method, based on the Linearized Euler Equations (LEE). In addition to the predicted tones, propeller-blade trailing edge noise is predicted with a RANS-CAA toolchain based on RANS simulations of multiple 2D propeller-blade airfoil sections, which provide the background meanflow for the Acoustic Perturbation Equations (APE), and also the necessary turbulence parameters to the Fast Random Particle Method (FRPM), for the generation of a source term in the APE. Both tonal and broadband noise predictions are non-empiric by definition, and do not require rotating grids for the corresponding simulation. For the tonal noise predictions, the pressure fluctuations at prescribed far-field microphone locations can be either probed directly in the CAA computational domain, or obtained from a permeable-surface FW-H acoustic analogy propagation.

Both numerical approaches are applied on a single propeller configuration in an isolated and installed arrangement, operating in forward flight. Propeller thrust, torque, tonal and broadband noise levels are compared with measurements data obtained in an aeroacoustic wind tunnel at a freestream speed of $U_\infty = 12 \text{ m s}^{-1}$ and $U_\infty = 24 \text{ m s}^{-1}$, to assess the capability of each numerical method to capture the measured acoustic levels.

II. Methodology

A. Experimental Setup

The experiments were conducted at the University of Bristol's aeroacoustic facility, an anechoic closed-circuit open-jet wind tunnel specifically designed for aerodynamic and aeroacoustic studies. The maximum free stream velocity is 32 m/s, with a turbulent intensity of around 0.2%. The exit nozzle measures 0.5 m in width and 0.775 m in height, with a contraction ratio of 8.4. The anechoic room's exposed surfaces, including the chamber and contraction nozzle, are either acoustically lined or covered with acoustic foam wedges to completely absorb any sound reflections. According to the ISO 3745 standardized testing procedure for both pure tone and broadband testing, the anechoic chamber permits measurements down to 160 Hz [24]. The experimental data and detailed methodology are publicly available in the work of Turhan *et al.* [20, 23].

Fig. 1 Schematic showing the experimental setup of the single-propeller wing.

As shown in Fig. 1, the experimental setup consists of a propulsion unit with the propeller mounted on a wing and a far-field microphone array. The experiments were performed with 5-bladed propeller with a diameter of $D = 9''$ (228.6 mm) and a pitch-to-diameter ratio of $P/D = 1$. The propellers, manufactured by Mejzlik (<https://www.mejzlik.eu/>), were made from carbon fiber/epoxy-based materials and had a Clark-Y aerofoil section. The blade chord and pitch angle distribution along the blade span are provided in Fig 2. The wing, with a chord of $c = 0.3$ m and a span of $L = 0.94$ m, had a NACA0018 profile and was made of 6000 series aluminium. The propeller was mounted at a distance of 97 mm from the center of the wing leading-edge and approximately 500 mm away from the nozzle exit. The 5-bladed propeller was attached to a propulsion unit that included a high-performance brushless motor, a 35A KDE-UAS35HVC electronic speed controller (ESC). The KDE4012XF-400 Brushless motor (1 kW) was used to drive the propeller, and the speed was controlled by an electronic speed controller (ESC). The rotational speed of the propeller was measured by a laser tachometer (Monarch 6180-029 ROLS-P), which was mounted on the left side of the test rig to create a closed loop with LabView code to control RPM. In this study, the rotation of the propeller was maintained constant at 8000 rpm with an accuracy of ± 5 rpm.

Fig. 2 Distribution of the blade chord length (c/R) and the pitch angle for the 5-bladed 9'' \times 9'' propeller used in this study.

The overhead array comprises 23 microphones, measuring polar angles from 40° to 140° with an increment of 5° . The microphones exhibit a frequency range of $f = 10$ Hz to 20 kHz, dynamic ranges of 142 dB, and an accuracy of ± 1 dB. Data are acquired at a sampling frequency of 2^{16} Hz. The microphones are calibrated using a G.R.A.S 42AA pistonphone calibrator before and after the experiments. Data acquisition is performed using a National Instruments PXIe01926Q chassis, with noise data acquired through the sound and vibration PXIe-4499 module with sampling frequency for $t = 32$ s.

B. LBM/VLES Computational Setup

The computational setup was realized as a free-field setup, which provides comparable results with the experimental configuration. The simulations were carried out using the PowerFLOW[®] solver, which employs a Lattice-Boltzmann Method combined with Very Large Eddy Simulation (LBM/VLES). The isolated propeller case was simulated using the 3D automated workflow for rotor aeroacoustic, similar to the method used by Casalino et al. [25]. This setup was then modified to introduce the downstream wing, with additional refinement regions to accommodate the wing-propeller interaction, following methods used in previous studies [26].

The simulation domain is defined as a spherical volume with a $400D$ radius, centered on the propeller. A free-stream boundary condition is applied along the outer boundary, with initial velocity $U_\infty = 12$ ms⁻¹, aligned along the x-axis. To emulate the anechoic chamber from the experimental setup, an acoustic sponge layer is included between a $200D$ radius inner sphere and the outer boundary. Within this layer, the fluid's kinematic viscosity is gradually increased from physical values to an artificially high level to dissipate outgoing acoustic waves and avoid reflections, similar to techniques used by Romani et al. [27]. To suppress tip vortices and ensure proper wake development, a circular side plate with a radius equal to the wing chord was attached to one side of the wing. Far-field noise predictions were carried out with the FW-H acoustic analogy, using pressure data collected from the relevant surfaces—namely propeller blades, hub, and wing. Figure 3 shows a close-up view of the propeller-wing setup with the Variable-Resolution (VR) regions. These regions refine the mesh equally in all dimensions, with each refinement level scaling the Cartesian cells (voxels) by a factor of two in each direction—that is, each voxel becomes $1/8^{\text{th}}$ of its previous volume. The computational domain is discretised with 16 VR regions, numbered 0 through 15.

Fig. 3 Variable Resolution (VR) regions around the propeller-wing set.

Near the propeller and wing, finer VR levels (13-15) ensure a highly detailed representation, with the smallest cell sizes along the blade's leading and trailing edges. Coarser VR levels beyond the immediate vicinity of the propeller are represented as concentric spheres, for a sharp coarsening at minimal computational cost. The computational meshes for both the isolated and installed propeller setups were constructed with the resources and knowledge available at the time. The isolated setup mesh contained approximately 1.44×10^8 voxels, while the installed setup mesh consisted of approximately 2.52×10^8 voxels. The smallest voxel edge length achieved in both cases was 5.79×10^{-5} m.

It should be noted that, due to limitations in mesh resolution and refinement strategy, these discretizations may be considered coarse relative to the fine-scale flow features and detailed aeroacoustic phenomena of interest. This may affect the accuracy of the results, particularly in capturing small-scale wake structures and the associated noise generation mechanisms. The PowerFLOW simulations were conducted using a time step size of 8.639×10^{-8} s for both configurations. Despite the relatively coarse mesh, this time step was chosen to ensure numerical stability and to resolve the main unsteady flow characteristics. Future work will aim to improve mesh quality and resolution to enhance simulation fidelity and more accurately capture the relevant physical phenomena.

C. RANS-CAA Methodology

1. RANS-CAA Mid-fidelity Model

The method employed consists of an hybrid CFD-CAA approach, in which the Linearized Euler Equations (LEE) are used in combination with a rotor modelling strategy for the rotor tonal noise component, based on representing loading noise and thickness noise contributions in terms of equivalent body sources. The rotor noise model is based on the approach introduced in [28], in which the rotor sources are modeled as three-dimensionally Gaussian regularised line-distributed input forces, rotating uniformly around the rotor axis. The line-distributed source values are specified from AD RANS solutions, allowing to solve for the perturbed variables on a background flow solution that includes the aerodynamic effect of a propeller. The rotor load values obtained from the RANS solver are required to be prescribed on a two-dimensional circular surface, as exemplified in Fig. (4).

To define the appropriate source distributions from the AD RANS solution, the line sources are defined on the computational grid based on a local cylindrical coordinate system centered at the rotor hub being modeled. The line-distributed sources can be defined as straight or piecewise linear curves, at an initial location $\vec{X}_{init} = (r_{init}, \phi_{init}, x_{init})^T$ and with an initial strength at each radial location on the lines which reads as $w = 1/N_{blade}$. If the rotor being modeled consists of multiple blades N_{blade} , the initial location of each line-distributed source is determined assuming an equi-spaced circumferential offset $2\pi/N_{blade}$ applied to ϕ_{init} .

Fig. 4 Actuator disc RANS solution example.

Fig. 5 Cylindrical coordinate system for a line-distributed source.

Figure (5) shows the geometrical quantities of interest. The preliminary defined line-distributed sources are then regularised with a two step-procedure, based on the consideration that for straight or piecewise linear curves the radial preliminary source strength value is already known. In the first step the value at a given radial grid location r_{Grid} is obtained by linear interpolation of the initial strength value in the range $[r_i, r_{i+1}]$, resulting in $\vec{f}_{Interp} = (f_{Interp,r}, f_{Interp,\phi}, f_{Interp,x})^T$. The interpolation performed in the first step reduces the necessary dimensions over which regularising is required, so that in the second step the regularisation of the preliminary line sources is obtained by convolution of \vec{f}_{Interp} with the Gaussian kernel $K(\phi_{Src}, x_{Src}, \phi_{Grid}, x_{Grid})$, defined as:

$$K(\phi_{Src}, x_{Src}, \phi_{Grid}, x_{Grid}) = \left(\frac{\ln(2)}{\pi} \right) \frac{1}{\varepsilon^2} \exp \left(\frac{-\ln(2)d_{LineSrc}^2}{\varepsilon^2} \right) / \text{erf} \left(\frac{\pi\sqrt{\ln(2)}r_{Src}}{\varepsilon} \right), \quad (1)$$

in which

$$d = \sqrt{r_{Src}^2 (\phi_{Src} - \phi_{Grid})^2 + (x_{Src} - x_{Grid})^2}, \quad (2)$$

is the distance measured on a cylindrical surface defined at a radius r_{Src} , where ϕ_{Src} is the line source azimuthal location, ϕ_{Grid} the grid point azimuthal coordinate, x_{Src} the line source axial location, and x_{Grid} the grid point axial coordinate. The variable ε represents the half-width at half-maximum of the Gaussian kernel. The Gaussian kernel $K(\phi_{Src}, x_{Src}, \phi_{Grid}, x_{Grid})$ is derived from a 2D Gaussian Kernel independent of the r coordinate, and averaged with an integration over the circumference, so that the resulting projected source, if integrated over the computational domain, would correspond to a unitary strength value. The error function term erf appearing at the denominator $K(\phi_{Src}, x_{Src}, \phi_{Grid}, x_{Grid})$ results from the integration, and for a given radius r_{Src} represents a constant scale factor. Figure (6), Fig. (7), and Fig. (8) show a possible definition of line sources from a given rotor blades geometry, and its corresponding line source regularisation with the procedure described.

Fig. 6 Original rotor blades to be modelled.

Fig. 7 Line sources of constant strength w , defined from the original rotor blades.

Fig. 8 Regularisation of line sources of strength w .

Fig. 9 Rotor sources from multiplication of interpolated AD sources with the line-distributed sources of preliminary strength.

The regularised source values obtained from Eq. (1) are described as the sum of a steady mean and a fluctuating component, where only the fluctuating component is of interest for the system of perturbation equations considered.

Hence, the perturbed regularised force values are calculated as $\vec{S}' = \vec{S} - S_{mean}^{\vec{}}$, where the mean value $S_{mean}^{\vec{}}$ is computed as the average source value over a rotor revolution, which in the case of constant rotational speed can be alternatively expressed as a spatial integral over a ring of given radius. After the regularisation of the preliminary sources of constant strength w , the related fluctuating sources' values \vec{S}' are multiplied with the load values on the AD surface, which is obtained through a Lagrangian high-order interpolator at a given radial and azimuthal coordinate on the circular surface. Figure (9) illustrates a possible line source distribution definition. The result of the multiplication is in the end scaled by the local circumference for a given radius, and assigned to the appropriate point of the FD discretization.

The described procedure ensures that the integrated line-distributed sources values correspond to the original load values on the AD surface, and it is applied at each time dependent source location identified by the circumferential coordinate ϕ_{time} , updated according to the sources revolutions per second n prescribed in input.

The system of perturbation equations in which the rotor tonal noise model is applied is the LEE in the primitive variables form, presented here in vector notation:

$$\frac{\partial \rho'}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho_0 \vec{u}' + \rho' \vec{u}_0) = \dot{\theta}', \quad (3)$$

$$\frac{\partial \vec{u}'}{\partial t} + (\vec{u}_0 \cdot \nabla) \vec{u}' + (\vec{u}' \cdot \nabla) \vec{u}_0 + \frac{\nabla p'}{\rho_0} - \rho' \frac{\nabla p_0}{\rho_0^2} = \frac{\vec{f}'}{\rho_0}, \quad (4)$$

$$\frac{\partial p'}{\partial t} + \vec{u}_0 \cdot \nabla p' + \vec{u}' \cdot \nabla p_0 + \gamma p_0 \nabla \cdot \vec{u}' + \gamma p' \nabla \cdot \vec{u}_0 = \frac{c_0^2}{\gamma} \dot{\theta}', \quad (5)$$

where ρ , \vec{u} , p , t , and γ are respectively the density, velocity, pressure, time, and specific heat ratio of air, with subscript 0 indicating mean flow quantities and primed symbols indicating perturbation quantities. $\dot{\theta}'$ represents rotor air displacement type of sources, and \vec{f}' externally prescribed rotor fluctuating forces of the LEE.

A system of equations like the LEE is the appropriate choice for the modelled rotor sources because the sources would require a system of equations in which both acoustic and non-acoustic eigenmodes are present. In a first attempt, the rotor sources were considered applied to the Acoustic Perturbation Equations (APE) [29], but the results initially obtained proved that the rotor sources cannot be applied directly to this system of equations, due to the assumptions made on its derivation. An additional source filtering would be required in order to use the APE as perturbation equations, which has no known closed form solution at the moment for a regularised source. If the APE are combined with a system of equations describing the non-acoustic eigenmodes, then the application of the rotor sources is possible, as done in [30], in which a velocity split approach was applied to the LEE.

The model is applied in the time domain and was implemented in DLR's PIANO code. The simulations in PIANO are carried out on hierarchical Cartesian meshes that resolve geometries by means of an Immersed Boundary Condition (IBC) for the solid-wall surfaces. The 4th order Dispersion Relation-Preserving (DRP) scheme is used with explicit fourth-order Runge-Kutta (RK) time integration to solve linear governing equations describing the dynamics of small perturbations over a steady background flow field provided by precursor RANS simulation. Details of the rotor model and the PIANO IBC implementation can be found in [28] and [31] respectively.

In addition to the tonal noise prediction, a rotor trailing edge broadband noise (TE-BBN) prediction approach has been developed, based on [32]. The toolchain is based on RANS simulations of multiple 2D airfoil sections, which provide the background meanflow for the APE, and also the necessary turbulence parameters to the FRPM method [33] for the generation of a non-empirical source term in the APE. A 2D CAA simulation is then performed using the Discontinuous Galerkin DLR code DISCO [34], and the results obtained at given virtual microphones arranged in a circle in the 2D CAA domain are then corrected to account for the rotation of the rotor blade, the associated amplitude modulation and the variation of the distance to arbitrary evaluation points.

The SPL correction factors used are:

$$SPL_{Span} = 10 \log_{10} \left(\frac{L_{Sec.}}{L_{Sec.,Ref.}} \right), \quad (6)$$

with $L_{Sec.}$ the section span, and $L_{Sec.,Ref.} = 1$

$$SPL_{Distance} = 10 \log_{10} \left(\frac{d_{Sec.,CAA}}{d_{TEtoFarf.}} \right), \quad (7)$$

with $d_{Sec.,CAA}$ the radius of the 2D CAA virtual microphone circle, and $d_{TEtoFarf.}$ the distance from a 2D CAA virtual microphone to the farfield microphone for evaluation.

$$SPL_{2D-3D} = 10 \log_{10} \left(\frac{1.4}{\pi} \frac{L_{Sec.}}{d_{Sec.,CAA}} Ma_{Sec.} \right), \quad (8)$$

with Ma_{Sec} . the local section Mach number

$$SPL_{Amplitude} = 10 \log_{10} \left(\frac{\sin(\phi)}{(1 - |Ma_{Sec.}| \cos(\xi))^4} \right), \quad (9)$$

with ϕ the polar angle identifying the farfield microphone in a plane perpendicular to the 2D sectional trailing directivity, and ξ the angle between the vector of blade leading edge flow and the line connecting the trailing edge to the observer.

The correction factors are applied as:

$$SPL_{Corrected} = SPL_{Span} + SPL_{Distance} + SPL_{2D-3D} + SPL_{Amplitude} \quad (10)$$

Figure 10, summarises the 2D CFD-CAA toolchain for TE-BBN prediction, while Fig. 11 shows the reference frame considered for the propagation to the farfield of the 2D CAA trailing edge noise data generated by the toolchain, using Eq. 10.

Fig. 10 2D CFD-CAA trailing edge broadband noise toolchain summary.

Fig. 11 Reference frame for propagation to farfield of broadband noise data.

2. RANS-CAA Computational Setup

The computational setup for the simulated cases consists of 4 steps.

As a first step, an input table of the propeller blade geometrical parameters and lift and drag coefficients, computed at different sections along the blade span needs to be generated, in order to perform the 3D AD RANS simulations. For the lift and drag values, 2D RANS simulations were conducted for given airfoil sections extracted from the blade geometry.

The next step consists in generating the 3D AD RANS simulations setup, defined as an external flow setup, where the section of interest of the wing span is simulated for the installed case. In this setup, the nacelle was not included. An hybrid computational mesh was generated of approximately 7 million cells for the installed case, whereas for the isolated case a grid of about 1 million cells was considered.

A detail of the grids generated can be seen in Fig. 12 and Fig. 13. The boundary conditions used in these setups, together with the TAU ad-hoc AD boundary condition, are:

- of viscous wall type for the wing,
- of symmetry type for the spanwise boundaries
- of farfield type for the remaining boundaries

For all the above RANS simulations, including the 2D airfoil sections, the DLR's TAU solver was used [35] and for the turbulence model, the SST model of Menter was selected [36].

Fig. 12 RANS grid, isolated configuration Fig. 13 RANS grid, installed configuration

After the 3D AD RANS simulations, the 3D CAA setup is generated, consisting of a hierarchical Cartesian grid with a refinement region around the propeller modelled, and a refinement region around the wing, if present (Fig. 14 and Fig. 15). Five overall grid levels were considered, with smallest node spacing of 2.5 mm, for a total of approximately 140 million grid points. The boundary of the immersed solid wall wing is assigned a no-slip wall boundary condition, whereas the remaining boundaries are assigned a Thompson type boundary condition. A total of 5 revolutions is simulated, with a time-step size of $2.94e - 05s$, which is sufficient to obtain an acoustic-transient-free solution. The pressure signal at the microphone locations depicted in Fig. 1 was obtained by directly probing the results in the CAA domain, without the need for extrapolation using the FW-H analogy.

As a last step, the TE-BBN prediction is computed based on the input solution of the AD obtained from the 3D RANS. From the AD results, the velocities are extracted at given radial locations along the propeller blade span, and azimuthal locations along the circumference of the disc in the propeller plane. For all the cases considered in this paper, a total of 15 radial sections along the propeller blade span, and 120 circumferential locations are considered, in order to capture possible non-uniformities and local flow conditions present in the AD solution. The airfoil profiles at the defined radial locations are then extracted from the blade geometry, and the corresponding 2D RANS simulation is setup based on this input. After that, the 2D CAA simulation input is determined from the corresponding 2D RANS results, and the results are collected for all radial and circumferential locations, and propagated to the far-field. The cases considered are related to $U_\infty = 12 \text{ m s}^{-1}$ and $U_\infty = 24 \text{ m s}^{-1}$, corresponding to $J = 0.39$ and $J = 0.78$ respectively.

Fig. 14 CAA grid detail, isolated configuration

Fig. 15 CAA grid detail, installed configuration

III. Results and Discussion

A. LBM/VLES Aerodynamic Performance of Propeller-Airfoil Configuration

To evaluate the aerodynamic performance of the propeller in forward flight, non-dimensional coefficients were used, following standard normalization practices. The advance ratio, J , which characterizes the relationship between the freestream velocity, U_∞ , and the propeller's rotation rate, is defined by

$$J = \frac{U_\infty}{nD}, \quad (11)$$

where n is the propeller's rotational rate and D the propeller diameter.

For the present simulations, an advance ratio of $J = 0.39$ was calculated from a freestream velocity $U_\infty = 12 \text{ m s}^{-1}$. Key aerodynamic parameters—including the thrust coefficient, C_T , and the torque coefficient, C_Q —were obtained using the following established formulas:

$$C_T = \frac{T}{\rho n^2 D^4}, \quad (12)$$

$$C_Q = \frac{Q}{\rho n^2 D^5}, \quad (13)$$

where T is the thrust, Q the torque and ρ the air density. The thrust and power coefficients were compared for the isolated and installed configurations, with results for advanced ratio $J = 0.39$ summarized in Table 1. Results from both isolated and installed propeller cases show a considerably divergence between thrust coefficients measured and calculated with numerical simulation (-25%). For the isolated propeller case the calculated torque presents a value -12% lower than the measured. The error for the torque on the installed propeller case is within -5% between the calculated and the measures values.

Table 1 LBM/VLES Aerodynamic Results for $J = 0.39$

Case	Method	C_T [-]	C_Q [-]
Isolated	Experiment	0.206	0.025
	Simulation	0.154	0.022
Installed	Experiment	0.211	0.024
	Simulation	0.157	0.023

In addition to aerodynamic metrics, the flow visualization for the installed case provided insight into wake interactions. By applying the λ_2 vortex criterion, the vortical structures around the propeller were identified, enabling an initial understanding of how the propeller blades' wake interacts with the wing. Figure 16 illustrates the λ_2 isosurfaces for a selected threshold ($\lambda_2 = -3.0 \times 10^6 \text{ 1/s}^2$), colored by velocity magnitude to depict the main flow structures and areas of vortex shedding.

The wake generated by the propeller blades displays large-scale vortices that are cut and stretched by the wing, leading to a dispersion on vortex structures on wing surface. This vortex interaction is particularly noticeable downstream of the wing leading edge where turbulent structures are deflected inboard in the upper surface and outboard in the lower surface.

The noise footprint, represented by the root-mean-square (RMS) of the pressure fluctuations (p') and presented in Figure 17, reveals distinct interaction patterns between the propeller tip vortices and the wing surfaces. On the wing's upper surface, the outboard region—where the propeller blade tips move upward—exhibits a nearly linear, undisturbed noise footprint path, indicating minimal deflection from the initial vortex trajectory. In contrast, the inboard region, where the blade tips transition from an upward to downward path, displays a deflected footprint that shifts inboard and decreases in intensity, likely due to the aerodynamic interaction and induced flow reorientation from the wing surface.

On the lower wing surface, the effect reverses. Here, the inboard noise footprint follows a straight trajectory, while the outboard footprint shows a notable outward deflection. This pattern suggests that the aerodynamic flow on the lower surface reorients the vortex path, causing the outboard footprint to veer outward as it progresses downstream. The asymmetry in footprint intensity and path deflection between the upper and lower surfaces underscores the impact of propeller rotation and wing surface position on noise distribution. These observations suggest that noise reduction strategies could benefit from adjustments in wing surface morphology to accommodate vortex paths, particularly in regions of intense tip vortex-wing interaction.

Fig. 16 λ_2 criterion of the wing-propeller simulation colored with velocity magnitude for the (a) isometric view, (b) front view and (c) top view.

B. LBM/VLES Aeroacoustic Characteristics of Propeller-Airfoil Configuration

In examining the aeroacoustic characteristics of a propeller in both isolated and installed configurations, this study analyzes the Sound Pressure Level (SPL) spectra and the directivity of the Overall Sound Pressure Level (OASPL) and single BPFs, derived from both experimental and the LBM/VLES numerical method.

Before delving into the specific characteristics of the noise spectra, it is essential to define the SPL calculation and address potential sources of spectral contamination. SPL is calculated from the power spectral density (PSD) of the pressure signals obtained at each microphone. The PSD provides a frequency resolution of $\Delta f = 8$ Hz, achieved by segmenting the time series data into equal-length data-segments with a 50% overlap, applying a Hamming window to reduce spectral leakage. The SPL spectrum is then determined by the equation:

$$\text{SPL} = 10 \log_{10} \left(\frac{\text{PSD}(f) \Delta f}{p_{\text{ref}}^2} \right), \quad (14)$$

where PSD is the power spectral density based on the unsteady pressure fluctuation $p'(t)$ (where $p'(t) = p(t) - p_{\text{mean}}$) and $p_{\text{ref}} = 20 \mu\text{Pa}$ is the reference pressure.

Fig. 17 Noise 'footprint' as the pressure fluctuation root-mean-square log computed on: (a) upper surface, (b) lower surface

This calculation framework, used for both experimental and LBM/VLES numerical SPL derivations, provides a standardized approach to analyzing the noise characteristics across the frequency range of interest, allowing for direct comparison of spectral components between configurations.

In Figure 18, the SPL spectra of the isolated propeller are compared across three observer angles ($\theta = 60^\circ$, $\theta = 90^\circ$, and $\theta = 120^\circ$) between experimental and LBM/VLES numerical data for an advance ratio $J = 0.39$. For low frequencies, experimental SPL levels exceed those predicted by the LBM/VLES numerical model, a discrepancy likely related to motor noise and other experimental factors unaccounted for in the simulations.

In addition to that, a distinct discrepancy arises around 1500 Hz , where motor noise components are hypothesized to influence the experimental results. Observer positioned at $\theta = 90^\circ$, located in the propeller plane, shows a high level of agreement at the BPF, from 41.8 dB on experiments to 41.6 dB on the LBM/VLES simulation (-0.5%). However, for off-plane observers ($\theta = 60^\circ$ upstream and $\theta = 120^\circ$ downstream), the LBM/VLES simulation underpredicts the experimental SPL, from 47.2 dB to 27.7 Hz (-41.3%) for $\theta = 60^\circ$ and from 46.6 dB to 40.3 dB (-13.5%) for $\theta = 120^\circ$, potentially due to the challenges of capturing wake interactions and propagation effects at these angles. Figure 18 also includes a detailed view surrounding the BPF region, highlighting close agreement in tonal components for observers from upstream up to plane observer, while showcasing the numerical model's limitations in accurately capturing upstream noise pattern for this configuration.

The set of data shown in Figure 19 provides the directivity patterns of the OASPL integrated from 600 Hz to 6666.7 Hz ($0.9 \times \text{BPF} - 10 \times \text{BPF}$) and the SPL of the BPF band for the isolated propeller, comparing the experimental and numerical results. For OASPL directivity, the experimental and numerical curves closely match in shape, though the numerical method overpredicts SPL by approximately 5 dB across most angles, which could be related to consistent overpredicted values for higher frequencies, over 2 k Hz .

In contrast, the directivity of the SPL in the BPF band shows a more complex and somewhat unexpected pattern in the experimental data, suggesting an intricate acoustic behavior that could benefit from additional analysis. From the directivities, both results present a downstream lobe, with a more pronounced intensity observed on experimental approach.

Fig. 18 Experimental and Numerical SPL plotted for the isolated propeller case at top arc and directivities: $\theta = 60^\circ$, $\theta = 90^\circ$ and $\theta = 120^\circ$ for an advance ratio $J = 0.39$. (a) Full spectra and (b) First BPF levels detail.

Fig. 19 Noise directivity for an advance ratio $J = 0.39$. (a) OASPL for the frequency range of 600–6666.7 Hz ($0.9 \times \text{BPF} - 10 \times \text{BPF}$) and (b) SPL at BPF plotted for the isolated propeller case.

For observers surrounding $\theta = 90^\circ$ there is a good agreement between results and the most discrepancy in shape is observed upstream, where experiment shown an increased lobe while the simulation presents a dip, surrounding $\theta = 60^\circ$. Figure 20 shows the SPL spectra at the same three observer positions for the installed configuration. For frequencies up to 2500 Hz, there is a good agreement between experimental and numerical results, and for higher

frequencies, numerical results present higher values.

Fig. 20 Experimental and Numerical SPL plotted for the installed propeller case at top arc and directivities: $\theta = 60^\circ$, $\theta = 90^\circ$ and $\theta = 120^\circ$ for an advance ratio $J = 0.39$. (a) Full spectra and (b) First BPF levels detail.

Regarding SPL in the BPF, the installed configuration presents more consistent values, presenting for $\theta = 90^\circ$ an overestimation of 3.1% (from 49.1 dB in experiments to 50.6 dB in simulations). For $\theta = 60^\circ$ numerical prediction slightly overestimates experimental results in 1.7% (from 46.6 dB to 47.4 dB) and downstream, for $\theta = 120^\circ$ numerical method overestimates experiments, from 51.4 dB to 55.4 dB (7.8%).

Figure 21 presents the directivity graphs for OASPL and BPF SPL for the installed configuration for both experimental and numerical sources. Similarly to the isolated configuration, the OASPL curves agree well in shape, with an approximate 5 dB mean difference. The SPL in the BPF, shown in Figure 21(b), also presents a good agreement in levels and shape when comparing experimental and numerical approaches, with an exception in a region upstream, where experimental results present a lobe that is not followed by the numerical approach.

To isolate the installation effects, Figure 22 compares the SPL spectra from the LBM/VLES simulations of the isolated and installed configurations. In general, all the observers present almost no difference on mean SPL levels for high frequencies (from approximately 2500 Hz), being the major difference for lower frequencies, with the installed configuration presenting higher level and with the most expressive change in the BPF.

The most significant change is observed at $\theta = 60^\circ$ in BPF, where the isolated case seems not to present a tonal peak, and the amplification at this point reaching 20 dB.

Figure 23 further highlights these effects in the directivity plots. From the OASPL plot we can see a similar shape in the curves for both configurations and a general increase on noise levels with an average offset of 1.5 dB upstream and a higher mean offset downstream (3.5 dB). A lobe rearwards for the installed configuration is also observed. Regarding the SPL in BPF, a change in the shape occurs, from multi-lobe curve, with a sharp dip surrounding $\theta = 60^\circ$, to a smooth curve with a considerable general offset. The numerical data clearly illustrate how the installation re-distributes the acoustic energy, concentrating it in the downstream direction. These patterns underline the importance of modeling installation features for accurate noise prediction, especially for observers

positioned downstream of the propulsion system.

Fig. 21 Noise directivity for an advance ratio $J = 0.39$. (a) OASPL for the frequency range of $600 - 6666.7$ Hz ($0.9 \times \text{BPF} - 10 \times \text{BPF}$) and (b) SPL at BPF plotted for the isolated propeller case.

Finally, Fig. 24 provides a direct comparison between experimental measurements of the isolated and installed configurations, focusing on OASPL and BPF SPL directivity. The OASPL plot shown small changes on installation, presenting a slight increase for observer in the plane of the propeller and also a small increase on the levels for observers upstream and downstream. Regarding the BPF SPL curves, we can see an increase on the downstream lobe width with a conservation of the shape and general levels of noise.

The combined insights from these analyses underscore a reasonable alignment between experimental and LBM/VLES numerical methods, particularly at the BPF for an observer in the plane of the propeller. However, some discrepancies—particularly in low-frequency SPL for the isolated configuration, and in downstream BPF directivities—highlight the need for further refinement in numerical models to capture the complex interactions between wake turbulence, motor noise, and propeller installation effects. For further investigations, additional numerical adjustments should be set to address these discrepancies and expand the validity of the predictive models for propeller aeroacoustic performance.

Fig. 22 Isolated and Installed propeller cases SPL calculated from LBM simulations and plotted at top arc and directivities: $\theta = 60^\circ$, $\theta = 90^\circ$ and $\theta = 120^\circ$ for an advance ratio $J = 0.39$. (a) Full spectra and (b) First BPF levels detail.

Fig. 23 Noise directivity for an advance ratio $J = 0.39$. Comparison for both calculated isolated and installed propeller cases on (a) OASPL for the frequency range of 600 – 6666.7 Hz (0.9xBPF - 10xBPF) and (b) SPL at BPF plotted for the isolated propeller case.

Fig. 24 Noise directivity for an advance ratio $J = 0.39$. Comparison for both measured isolated and installed propeller cases on (a) OASPL for the frequency range of 600 – 6666.7 Hz (0.9xBPF - 10xBPF) and (b) SPL at BPF plotted for the isolated propeller case.

C. Mid-fidelity RANS-CAA approach results

The results obtained from the RANS simulations are compared in Table 2 and Table 3 with the experimental integral values of thrust and torque coefficient, similarly as what done for the LBM/VLES predictions. The predicted thrust coefficient shows a closer agreement with the experiments than what obtained with the LBM/VLES predictions. For the $J = 0.39$ case, a reduction in thrust of 12% is seen for the isolated configuration, whereas for the installed configuration a reduction of 10% is obtained for the thrust. For the $J = 0.78$ case, a reduction in thrust of 14% can be seen for the isolated configuration, with the installed configuration showing a reduction of 17%. The predicted torque coefficient is in line with what obtained also with the LBM/VLES simulations. A reduction of about 10% approximately for both the $J = 0.39$ and $J = 0.78$ cases is seen, comparing RANS simulations with experiments.

Table 2 Mid-Fidelity RANS Aerodynamic Results for $J = 0.39$

Case	Method	C_T [-]	C_Q [-]
Isolated	Experiment	0.206	0.025
	Simulation	0.182	0.022
Installed	Experiment	0.211	0.024
	Simulation	0.189	0.022

Table 3 Mid-Fidelity RANS Aerodynamic Results for $J = 0.78$

Case	Method	C_T [-]	C_Q [-]
Isolated	Experiment	0.1304	0.0207
	Simulation	0.112	0.019
Installed	Experiment	0.1410	0.0212
	Simulation	0.117	0.019

The RANS results are shown in Fig. 25, Fig. 26, Fig. 27 and Fig. 28 in terms of contour plots of the velocity magnitude, highlighting the capabilities of the AD TAU model of capturing the change in slipstream for the installed configurations, when compared to the corresponding isolated setups. The CAA results obtained are shown first as contour plots in Fig. 29, Fig. 30, Fig. 31 and Fig. 32, to highlight qualitatively the capabilities of the rotor tonal noise prediction model. It can be seen that for both $J = 0.39$ and $J = 0.78$ cases, the installed configuration shows the strongest acoustic response downstream of the wing. Due to the chosen extent of the computational domain, it can also be seen that the initial transient vortical structure generated by the rotor model is still present in the solution, without affecting the acoustic field in the far-field or near the wing for the installed case.

Fig. 25 RANS solution, isolated configuration,
 $U_\infty = 12 \text{ m s}^{-1}, J = 0.39$

Fig. 26 RANS solution, installed configuration,
 $U_\infty = 12 \text{ m s}^{-1}, J = 0.39$

Fig. 27 RANS solution, isolated configuration,
 $U_{\infty} = 24 \text{ m s}^{-1}, J = 0.78$

Fig. 28 RANS solution, installed configuration,
 $U_{\infty} = 24 \text{ m s}^{-1}, J = 0.78$

A close-up view of the solution obtained is shown in Fig. 33 and Fig. 34, highlighting the convected propeller tip vortices originating from the rotating line-distributed sources, displayed with iso-contours of the Q-Criterion computed from the fluctuating velocity components of the LEE.

In addition to this, Figs. [35-40] show the narrow band spectra of the same mics considered in the LBM/VLES comparison, that is mics at $\theta = 60^\circ$, $\theta = 90^\circ$ and $\theta = 120^\circ$ for the case $J = 0.39$, to highlight the predicted tonal and broadband component. The narrow band spectra of the experimental data is obtained by applying the Welch method on the raw data signal, characterized by a number of samples of $N_{samples} = 2097152$ and a sampling frequency of $f_s = 2^{16}$. The Welch method was applied by segmenting the time series data into data-segments of length $(N_{samples}/N_{blade})$, with a 50% overlap, applying a Hamming window to reduce spectral leakage, resulting in a frequency resolution of $\Delta f = 0.15625 \text{ Hz}$. The choice of data-segments of length $(N_{samples}/N_{blade})$ allows to highlight distinctly the tonal and broadband noise levels of the experiments, removing noise from the data and without reducing the fidelity of the data by averaging over larger bandwidths. The obtained processed data was not scaled with the bandwidth Δf to obtain a PSD, but instead the squared magnitude spectrum was computed. The choice of not scaling the processed data was done to maintain the original tone amplitudes of the experimental narrow band spectra. When considering the $\theta = 60^\circ$ mic, the installed configuration shows a good agreement for the 1st and 2nd BPF, whereas the isolated configuration shows a noticeable difference of the predicted 1st BPF with the corresponding experimental value. The 2nd BPF is instead more closely captured for both the installed and isolated configuration. The decreasing trend of the propeller tones is well captured for both the installed and the isolated configuration at the $\theta = 90^\circ$ mic, and in particular a good agreement between simulations and measurements can be seen for the 1st and 2nd BPF. The comparison between the experimental data and the predicted values at the $\theta = 120^\circ$ mic shows a slight over-prediction of 3 dB for the 1st BPF of the installed configuration, whereas the 1st BPF of the isolated configuration is under-predicted of approximately 5 dB . Higher BPFs show deviations for both installed and isolated configurations when compared to the experiments.

Besides the comparison of narrow band spectra at selected microphone locations, the predicted directivities are also compared with the experiments for the case $J = 0.39$. Figure 41 and 42 show the comparison in terms of the 1st BPF, respectively for the isolated and installed configuration. A good agreement of the directivity curves can be observed on average, with the increase in SPL being captured for downstream microphones. The simulation results of the installed configuration show an over-prediction of approximately 5 dB downstream of the propeller, and before the $\theta = 60^\circ$ mic, a sudden increase in the experimental levels is seen, deviating from the simulation results of approximately 5 dB . For the isolated configuration, the experiments show a sudden increase in the regions near $\theta = 60^\circ$ and $\theta = 120^\circ$ that would need to be investigated more in detail. This increase in levels is not captured by the simulations, with a difference on average of $5 - 8 \text{ dB}$. The comparison in terms of the 2nd BPF is shown in Fig.43 and Fig.44, respectively for the isolated and installed configuration. For the isolated configuration, the directivity shape is captured on average, but an increase in SPL of approximately 5 dB is detected. For the installed configuration, an increase in SPL between 2 dB and 5 dB can be seen for the downstream region, whereas upstream a sudden decrease in levels can be noted, not found in the experiments.

Fig. 29 CAA solution, isolated configuration, $U_\infty = 12 \text{ m s}^{-1}$, $J = 0.39$

Fig. 30 CAA solution, installed configuration, $U_\infty = 12 \text{ m s}^{-1}$, $J = 0.39$

Fig. 31 CAA solution, isolated configuration, $U_\infty = 24 \text{ m s}^{-1}$, $J = 0.78$

Fig. 32 CAA solution, installed configuration, $U_\infty = 24 \text{ m s}^{-1}$, $J = 0.78$

Fig. 33 CAA solution with modelled tip vortices, isolated configuration, $U_\infty = 12 \text{ m s}^{-1}$, $J = 0.39$

Fig. 34 CAA solution with modelled tip vortices, installed configuration, $U_\infty = 12 \text{ m s}^{-1}$, $J = 0.39$

Fig. 35 Comparison of CAA results with experiments, narrow band plot, isolated configuration, $\theta = 60^\circ$, $U_\infty = 12 \text{ m s}^{-1}$, $J = 0.39$

Fig. 36 Comparison of CAA results with experiments, narrow band plot, installed configuration, $\theta = 60^\circ$, $U_\infty = 12 \text{ m s}^{-1}$, $J = 0.39$

Fig. 37 Comparison of CAA results with experiments, narrow band plot, isolated configuration, $\theta = 90^\circ$, $U_\infty = 12 \text{ m s}^{-1}$, $J = 0.39$

Fig. 38 Comparison of CAA results with experiments, narrow band plot, installed configuration, $\theta = 90^\circ$, $U_\infty = 12 \text{ m s}^{-1}$, $J = 0.39$

Fig. 39 Comparison of CAA results with experiments, narrow band plot, isolated configuration, $\theta = 120^\circ$, $U_\infty = 12 \text{ m s}^{-1}$, $J = 0.39$

Fig. 40 Comparison of CAA results with experiments, narrow band plot, installed configuration, $\theta = 120^\circ$, $U_\infty = 12 \text{ m s}^{-1}$, $J = 0.39$

In addition to case $J = 0.39$, the results for case $J = 0.78$ are also shown, to highlight the capabilities of the mid-fidelity RANS-CAA approach to capture different inflow conditions. Figures [35-40] show the narrow band spectra of the same mics considered in the LBM/VLES comparison, that is mics at $\theta = 60^\circ$, $\theta = 90^\circ$ and $\theta = 120^\circ$, highlighting the predicted tonal and broadband component. When considering the $\theta = 60^\circ$ mic, the installed configuration shows an under-prediction of the 1st BPF simulated values of 5 dB , whereas for the isolated configuration a reduction of about 10 dB is seen. As for the 2nd BPF values, a good agreement is seen for the isolated configuration, whereas the simulation results of the installed configuration show a reduction of about 10 dB . In the comparison for $\theta = 90^\circ$, a close agreement is seen for the 1st BPF, and the 2nd BPF shows a slight over-prediction of about 3 dB . At $\theta = 120^\circ$, the installed configuration shows a close agreement of the 1st BPF, whereas the 2nd BPF is noticeably over-predicted by approximately 15 dB . It must be noted though that in this particular case, the 2nd BPF of the experiment is almost non-existent, with levels comparable with broadband noise levels. A possible explanation for this is at the time of writing not available.

As already shown for the case $J = 0.39$, also for $J = 0.78$ the predicted directivities were compared with the experiments. Figure 51 and Fig. 52 show the comparison in terms of the 1st BPF, respectively for the isolated and installed configuration.

A good agreement of the directivity curve can be observed on average for the installed configuration, with the increase in SPL being captured for downstream microphones. The simulation results of the installed configuration show an over-prediction of approximately 3 dB downstream of the propeller, and before the $\theta = 60^\circ$ mic, a decrease in simulated levels of approximately 5 dB . For the isolated configuration, the experiments show the same sudden increase in the regions near $\theta = 60^\circ$ and $\theta = 120^\circ$, seen also for $J = 0.39$. This could indicate possibly an effect due to the experimental setup, which would need to be investigated more in detail. At $\theta = 90^\circ$, a close agreement between simulated and experimental results can be seen. The comparison in terms of the 2nd BPF is shown in Fig.53 and Fig.54, respectively for the isolated and installed configuration. For the isolated configuration, the directivity shape is captured on average, with an increase in SPL from 2 dB to 5 dB , depending on the location on the arc considered. For the installed configuration, the directivity curves differ, with lower levels of the experiments that are unexpected, considering the comparison seen for the $J = 0.39$ case. The reasons for this would need to be investigated.

Fig. 41 Comparison of CAA results with experiments, 1st BPF directivity, isolated configuration, $U_\infty = 12 \text{ m s}^{-1}$, $J = 0.39$

Fig. 42 Comparison of CAA results with experiments, 1st BPF directivity, installed configuration, $U_\infty = 12 \text{ m s}^{-1}$, $J = 0.39$

Fig. 43 Comparison of CAA results with experiments, 2nd BPF directivity, isolated configuration, $U_\infty = 12 \text{ m s}^{-1}$, $J = 0.39$

Fig. 44 Comparison of CAA results with experiments, 2nd BPF directivity, installed configuration, $U_\infty = 12 \text{ m s}^{-1}$, $J = 0.39$

Fig. 45 Comparison of CAA results with experiments, narrow band plot, isolated configuration, $\theta = 60^\circ$, $U_\infty = 24 \text{ m s}^{-1}$, $J = 0.78$

Fig. 46 Comparison of CAA results with experiments, narrow band plot, installed configuration, $\theta = 60^\circ$, $U_\infty = 24 \text{ m s}^{-1}$, $J = 0.78$

Fig. 47 Comparison of CAA results with experiments, narrow band plot, isolated configuration, $\theta = 90^\circ$, $U_\infty = 24 \text{ m s}^{-1}$, $J = 0.78$

Fig. 48 Comparison of CAA results with experiments, narrow band plot, installed configuration, $\theta = 90^\circ$, $U_\infty = 24 \text{ m s}^{-1}$, $J = 0.78$

Fig. 49 Comparison of CAA results with experiments, narrow band plot, isolated configuration, $\theta = 120^\circ$, $U_\infty = 24 \text{ m s}^{-1}$, $J = 0.78$

Fig. 50 Comparison of CAA results with experiments, narrow band plot, installed configuration, $\theta = 120^\circ$, $U_\infty = 24 \text{ m s}^{-1}$, $J = 0.78$

Fig. 51 Comparison of CAA results with experiments, 1st BPF directivity, isolated configuration, $U_\infty = 24 \text{ m s}^{-1}$, $J = 0.78$

Fig. 52 Comparison of CAA results with experiments, 1st BPF directivity, installed configuration, $U_\infty = 24 \text{ m s}^{-1}$, $J = 0.78$

Fig. 53 Comparison of CAA results with experiments, 2nd BPF directivity, isolated configuration, $U_\infty = 24 \text{ m s}^{-1}$, $J = 0.78$

Fig. 54 Comparison of CAA results with experiments, 2nd BPF directivity, installed configuration, $U_\infty = 24 \text{ m s}^{-1}$, $J = 0.78$

In summary, the comparison between the experiments and results from the mid-fidelity RANS/CAA approach shows a good agreement for both installed and isolated configuration at the two different advance ratios investigated, namely $J = 0.39$ and $J = 0.78$. It should be noted that the experiments include also effects such as tone haystacking, probably due to the propagation of sound waves through the shear layer of the jet from the wind tunnel's exit nozzle, which can alter the amplitude of certain tones. In addition to that, non-BPFs tones are present, which could be attributable to interactions of motor noise tones with propeller tones, or to blades-manufacturing non-uniformities. The consequence of these effects on the measured values is being investigated. Nevertheless, the experimentally acquired signals show a clear distinction between tones and broadband noise levels, making them suitable for validation and verification of numerical models.

D. Cross-comparison of numerical models with experiments

All the results obtained from the numerical models are here cross-compared, to highlight the capabilities of each numerical approach of capturing the relevant acoustic features. Figures [55-60] show the narrow band spectra of the same mics considered in the previous comparisons, for the case $J = 0.39$. The bandwidth of the experimental narrow band spectra was chosen to be $\Delta f = 0.15625$ Hz, which is the same bandwidth of the narrow band spectra of the figures included in Sec.III.C. This choice highlights the distinct tonal and broadband levels, allowing a more accurate comparison of the numerical results. The LBM/VLES results were scaled according to the experimental narrow band spectra bandwidth, maintaining the tones levels and scaling only the broadband part of the spectra. Overall it can be seen that the LBM/VLES setup realized over-predicts the broadband levels by approximately $2 - 3$ dB for the isolated configuration, with a closer agreement for the installed configuration. The mid-fidelity RANS/CAA approach shows an overall close prediction of the broadband noise levels, with over-predicted levels in a range within 2 dB and 5 dB. Figures [61-64] show the comparison in terms of the 1st BPF and 2nd BPF for the predicted values against the experimental data, for the case $J = 0.39$ and both installed and isolated configuration. For the isolated configuration, the directivity shape is captured on average by the mid-fidelity RANS/CAA approach. As highlighted already, the experimental values of the 1st BPF show a sudden increase around $\theta = 60^\circ$ and $\theta = 120^\circ$ that is not captured by the simulations, with an increase in SPL from 8 dB to 10 dB, depending on the location on the arc considered. The LBM/VLES results show a close agreement of the values at $\theta = 90^\circ$, whereas for $\theta = 60^\circ$, values are under-predicted of approximately 30 dB. An under-prediction of 3 dB is detected at $\theta = 120^\circ$.

Fig. 55 Comparison of LBM/VLES and CAA results with experiments, narrow band plot, isolated configuration, $\theta = 60^\circ$, $U_\infty = 12 \text{ m s}^{-1}$, $J = 0.39$

Fig. 56 Comparison of LBM/VLES and CAA results with experiments, narrow band plot, installed configuration, $\theta = 60^\circ$, $U_\infty = 12 \text{ m s}^{-1}$, $J = 0.39$

Fig. 57 Comparison of LBM/VLES and CAA results with experiments, narrow band plot, isolated configuration, $\theta = 90^\circ$, $U_\infty = 12 \text{ m s}^{-1}$, $J = 0.39$

Fig. 58 Comparison of LBM/VLES and CAA results with experiments, narrow band plot, installed configuration, $\theta = 90^\circ$, $U_\infty = 12 \text{ m s}^{-1}$, $J = 0.39$

Fig. 59 Comparison of LBM/VLES and CAA results with experiments, narrow band plot, isolated configuration, $\theta = 120^\circ$, $U_\infty = 12 \text{ m s}^{-1}$, $J = 0.39$

Fig. 60 Comparison of LBM/VLES and CAA results with experiments, narrow band plot, installed configuration, $\theta = 120^\circ$, $U_\infty = 12 \text{ m s}^{-1}$, $J = 0.39$

For the 2nd BPF, the LBM/VLES values are under-predicted of approximately 10dB at $\theta = 90^\circ$, as well as for $\theta = 60^\circ$ and for $\theta = 120^\circ$. The mid-fidelity RANS/CAA results for the 2nd BPF show a closer agreement, but overall an over-prediction of values from 5dB to 10dB , depending on the arc location considered. It should be pointed out that the directivity shape of the 2nd BPF shows rapidly varying values that are probably difficult to capture by any numerical model considered.

For the installed configuration, the directivity curves of both the LBM/VLES and the RANS/CAA approach show a very close agreement with the measured experimental values of the 1st BPF, highlighting how both numerical approaches can capture the main installation effects for tonal noise predictions. The close agreement of the numerical results with the experiments can be detected also for the 2nd BPF, for which both models predict similar values in the region downstream of the propeller, whereas discrepancies are found in the upstream region. In particular at $\theta = 60^\circ$, both numerical approaches show values under-predicted by almost 10dB .

Overall it can be stated that the numerical methods considered can provide an acceptable prediction of the experimental values considered in this paper, whereas for the broadband noise levels a conclusive statement cannot be considered at the time of writing, due to the coarseness of the LBM/VLES setup. It could only be stated that the mid-fidelity RANS/CAA approach shows a close agreement to the broadband noise levels on average.

Fig. 61 Comparison of CAA results with experiments, 1st BPF directivity, isolated configuration, $U_\infty = 12 \text{ m s}^{-1}$, $J = 0.39$

Fig. 62 Comparison of CAA results with experiments, 1st BPF directivity, installed configuration, $U_\infty = 12 \text{ m s}^{-1}$, $J = 0.39$

Fig. 63 Comparison of CAA results with experiments, 2nd BPF directivity, isolated configuration, $U_\infty = 12 \text{ m s}^{-1}$, $J = 0.39$

Fig. 64 Comparison of CAA results with experiments, 2nd BPF directivity, installed configuration, $U_\infty = 12 \text{ m s}^{-1}$, $J = 0.39$

E. Comparison of the computational cost of the numerical models

The PowerFLOW[®] simulation is conducted in two stages: an initial Coarse Simulation phase, used to adjust and accommodate the simulation parameters, followed by a Fine Simulation, which represents the final, higher-resolution analysis. Complementing this approach, the PowerACOUSTICS[®] suite is employed to compute pressure fluctuations at predefined observer locations using the FW-H analogy.

The RANS-CAA simulation comprises the four steps described in Section II.C.2.

Table 4 summarizes the computational costs associated with each simulation stage across the different approaches.

Table 4 Summary of Computational Costs (in CoreHours)

	Simulation	Cores	Hours	CoreHours
PowerFLOW Isolated	Coarse	255	6.6	1683
	Fine	255	43.7	11144
	FW-H Calculation	14	10	140
	Total			12967
PowerFLOW Installed	Coarse	255	12.7	3239
	Fine	255	66.9	17060
	FW-H Calculation	14	10	140
	Total			20439
RANS-CAA Isolated	2D RANS (15 sections)	1920	1.5	2880
	3D AD RANS	320	0.06	19
	3D CAA tonal prediction	1280	5.5	7080
	2D RANS-CAA TE-BBN prediction (15 sections)	1920	18.5	35520
	Total			45500
RANS-CAA Installed	2D RANS (15 sections)	1920	1.5	2880
	3D AD RANS	1280	0.7	896
	3D CAA tonal prediction	1280	5.5	7080
	2D RANS-CAA TE-BBN prediction (15 sections)	1920	18.5	35520
	Total			46376

For predicting the tonal component of the acoustic response of a propeller, based on the setups generated, the PowerFLOW[®] LBM/VLES approach would require a computational cost of approximately 23% more than the mid-fidelity RANS/CAA approach for an isolated configuration (LBM/VLES: 12967*CoreHours*, RANS/CAA: 9979*CoreHours*). For an installed configuration, the PowerFLOW[®] LBM/VLES approach would require an increase of about 47% in the computational cost (LBM/VLES: 20439*CoreHours*, RANS/CAA: 10856*CoreHours*), due to the additional refinement required for the wing. As for the computational cost required for a simulation that would include tonal and propeller blade TE-BBN components, as stated in Section II.B, the PowerFLOW[®] grid setup realized might be too coarse to resolve the the fine-scale flow features and detailed aeroacoustic phenomena of interest, therefore no conclusive comparison could be considered. Since the computational cost mentioned in Table 4 for the mid-fidelity RANS/CAA approach would not require a change in resolution for the comprehensive tonal and propeller blade TE-BBN components, it can be stated that approximately 45000*CoreHours* would be required to obtain the acoustic response of an installed propeller. As a future development of the TE-BBN prediction tool, it is planned to replace the Discontinuous Galerkin code DISCO with the more efficient PIANO IBC implementation for 2D airfoils, to reduce the computational cost of the 2D CAA simulations, which at the moment amount to approximately 90% of the total.

IV. Summary

The aeroacoustic performance of the Mejzlik 9x9 propeller was compared through experimental and numerical methods, comprising isolated and Installed configurations and the resulting noise characteristics at different observer positions. Numerical predictions at three distinct observers at angles ($\theta = 60^\circ, 90^\circ, \text{ and } 120^\circ$) revealed areas of strong agreement with experimental results, particularly at the blade passing frequency (BPF) for observers at the plane of the propeller. However, notable discrepancies were observed in low-frequency SPL levels and directivities at off-plane angles, suggesting the need for further refinement of the LBM setup.

The analysis of OASPL directivity and BPF tonal components highlighted the LBM framework's ability to replicate general trends while exposing its limitations in capturing upstream and downstream noise patterns influenced by complex wake interactions and installation-specific effects. These limitations are partly attributed to the mesh resolution adopted in the PowerFLOW simulations, which, due to practical constraints, may be considered coarse for accurately resolving small-scale wake features and aeroacoustic sources. Despite this, the time step used ensured numerical stability and the capture of dominant unsteady flow structures.

The results of the mid-fidelity RANS-CAA approach highlight the capabilities of the method in capturing the BPFs and the broadband noise levels. In particular, the acoustic response of installed configurations was in close agreement with the experiments, while the predictions for isolated configurations showed some discrepancies which could be attributed to the specific experimental setup considered.

In terms of computational efficiency of the numerical methods considered, it can be stated that the mid-fidelity RANS/CAA approach can provide a prediction in approximately half the computational cost of the LBM/VLES method considered. A detailed comparison of broadband noise predictions was not attempted due to the coarseness of the LBM/VLES setup. Future work will prioritize improved mesh generation and refinement strategies to enhance simulation fidelity and the accurate capture of relevant physical phenomena.

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